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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to study Lorentzian special Sasakian manifolds and generalized Lorentzian Co-symplectic manifolds [1] with semi-symmetric metric connection [3].

KEYWORDS: Nearly and almost LS-Sasakian manifolds, generalized L-Co-symplectic manifolds, semi-symmetric metric connection, Nijenhuis tensor [2].

INTRODUCTION

An n-dimensional differentiable manifold M_n , on which there are defined a tensor field F of type $(1, 1)$, a vector field T , a 1-form A and a Lorentzian metric g , satisfying for arbitrary vector fields X, Y, Z, \dots

$$(1.1) \quad \bar{X} = -X - A(X)T, \quad \bar{T} = 0, \quad A(T) = -1, \quad \bar{X} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} FX, \quad A(\bar{X}) = 0, \quad \text{rank } F = n - 1.$$

$$(1.2) \quad g(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) = g(X, Y) + A(X)A(Y), \text{ where } A(X) = g(X, T), \\ \bar{F}(X, Y) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} g(\bar{X}, Y) = -F(Y, X),$$

Then M_n is called a Lorentzian contact manifold (an L-Contact manifold).

Let D be a Riemannian connection on M_n , then

An L-Contact manifold is called a Lorentzian special Sasakian manifold (an LS-Sasakian manifold), if

$$(1.3) \quad (a) \quad (D_X F)(Y) + A(Y)\bar{X} - \bar{F}(X, Y)T = 0 \Leftrightarrow (D_X \bar{F})(Y, Z) - A(Y)\bar{F}(Z, X) - A(Z)\bar{F}(X, Y) = 0 \\ (b) \quad D_X T = \bar{X}$$

An L-Contact manifold is called a nearly Lorentzian special Sasakian manifold (a nearly LS-Sasakian manifold), if

$$(1.4) \quad (D_X \bar{F})(Y, Z) - A(Y)\bar{F}(Z, X) - A(Z)\bar{F}(X, Y) \\ = (D_Y \bar{F})(Z, X) - A(Z)\bar{F}(X, Y) - A(X)\bar{F}(Y, Z) \\ = (D_Z \bar{F})(X, Y) - A(X)\bar{F}(Y, Z) - A(Y)\bar{F}(Z, X)$$

An L-Contact manifold is called an almost Lorentzian special Sasakian manifold (an almost LS-Sasakian manifold), if

$$(1.5) \quad (D_X \bar{F})(Y, Z) + (D_Y \bar{F})(Z, X) + (D_Z \bar{F})(X, Y) - 2\{A(X)\bar{F}(Y, Z) + A(Y)\bar{F}(Z, X) + A(Z)\bar{F}(X, Y)\} = 0$$

An L-Contact manifold is called a generalized Lorentzian Co-symplectic manifold (a generalized L-Co-symplectic manifold), if

$$(1.6) \quad (a) \quad (D_X F)Y - A(Y)\bar{D}_X T - (D_X A)(\bar{Y})T = 0 \Leftrightarrow \\ (b) \quad (D_X \bar{F})(Y, Z) + A(Y)(D_X A)(\bar{Z}) - A(Z)(D_X A)(\bar{Y}) = 0$$

An L-Contact manifold is called a generalized nearly Lorentzian Co-symplectic manifold (a generalized nearly L-Co-symplectic manifold), if

$$(1.7) \quad (D_X \bar{F})(Y, Z) + A(Y)(D_X A)(\bar{Z}) - A(Z)(D_X A)(\bar{Y}) \\ = (D_Y \bar{F})(Z, X) + A(Z)(D_Y A)(\bar{X}) - A(X)(D_Y A)(\bar{Z}) \\ = (D_Z \bar{F})(X, Y) + A(X)(D_Z A)(\bar{Y}) - A(Y)(D_Z A)(\bar{X})$$

An L-Contact manifold is called a generalized almost L-Co-symplectic manifold, if

$$(1.8) \quad (D_X \bar{F})(Y, Z) + (D_Y \bar{F})(Z, X) + (D_Z \bar{F})(X, Y) - A(X)\{(D_Y A)(\bar{Z}) - (D_Z A)(\bar{Y})\} \\ - A(Y)\{(D_Z A)(\bar{X}) - (D_X A)(\bar{Z})\} - A(Z)\{(D_X A)(\bar{Y}) - (D_Y A)(\bar{X})\} = 0$$

SEMI-SYMMETRIC METRIC CONNECTION

Let us consider a connection B on M_n , defined by

$$(2.1) \quad B_X Y \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} D_X Y + A(Y)X - g(X, Y)T$$

The torsion tensor S of B is given by

$$(2.2) \quad S(X, Y) = A(Y)X - A(X)Y$$

Further, if $(B_X g) = 0$, then B is called a semi-symmetric metric connection.

Put

$$(2.3) \quad (a) \quad B_X Y = D_X Y + H(X, Y)$$

Where H is a tensor field of type $(1, 2)$, then

- (b) $H(X, Y) = A(Y)X - g(X, Y)T$
- (c) $\nabla H(X, Y, Z) = A(Y)g(Z, X) - A(Z)g(X, Y)$
- (d) $\nabla S(X, Y, Z) = \nabla H(X, Y, Z) - \nabla H(Y, X, Z)$

Where

$$\nabla H(X, Y, Z) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} g(H(X, Y), Z) \quad \text{and} \quad \nabla S(X, Y, Z) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} g(S(X, Y), Z)$$

In an L-Contact manifold, we have

$$(2.4) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) + (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) + A(Y)(B_X A)(\bar{Z}) - A(Z)(B_X A)(\bar{Y}) = 0$$

Therefore,

An L-Contact manifold is called an LS-Sasakian manifold, if

$$(2.5) \quad (a) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) - 2A(Y)\nabla F(Z, X) - 2A(Z)\nabla F(X, Y) = 0$$

$$(b) \quad B_X T = 2\bar{X}$$

On this manifold, we have

$$(2.6) \quad (a) \quad (B_X A)(\bar{Y}) = 2\nabla F(X, Y) \Leftrightarrow (b) \quad (B_X A)(Y) = -2g(\bar{X}, \bar{Y})$$

An L-contact manifold is called a nearly LS-Sasakian manifold, if

$$(2.7) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) - 2A(Y)\nabla F(Z, X) - 2A(Z)\nabla F(X, Y) \\ = (B_Y \nabla F)(Z, X) - 2A(Z)\nabla F(X, Y) - 2A(X)\nabla F(Y, Z) \\ = (B_Z \nabla F)(X, Y) - 2A(X)\nabla F(Y, Z) - 2A(Y)\nabla F(Z, X)$$

The equation of a nearly LS-Sasakian manifold can also be written as

$$(2.8) \quad (a) \quad (B_X \nabla F)Y + (B_Y \nabla F)X + 2A(Y)\bar{X} + 2A(X)\bar{Y} = 0 \Leftrightarrow \\ (b) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) - (B_Y \nabla F)(Z, X) - 2A(Y)\nabla F(Z, X) + 2A(X)\nabla F(Y, Z) = 0$$

These equations can be modified as

$$(2.9) \quad (a) \quad (B_X \nabla F)\bar{Y} + (B_{\bar{Y}} \nabla F)X + 2A(X)\bar{Y} = 0 \Leftrightarrow \\ (b) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(\bar{Y}, Z) - (B_{\bar{Y}} \nabla F)(Z, X) - 2A(X)g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) = 0$$

$$(2.10) \quad (a) \quad (B_X \nabla F)\bar{Y} + (B_{\bar{Y}} \nabla F)X - 2A(X)\bar{Y} = 0 \Leftrightarrow \\ (b) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(\bar{Y}, Z) - (B_{\bar{Y}} \nabla F)(Z, X) - 2A(X)\nabla F(Y, Z) = 0$$

$$(2.11) \quad (a) \quad (B_X \nabla F)Y + (B_Y \nabla F)X - A(Y)\{B_X T - (B_T F)X\} - A(X)\{B_Y T - (B_T F)Y\} = 0 \Leftrightarrow \\ (b) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) - (B_Y \nabla F)(Z, X) + A(Y)\{(B_X A)(\bar{Z}) - (B_T \nabla F)(Z, X)\} + A(X)\{(B_Y A)(\bar{Z}) - (B_T \nabla F)(Z, Y)\} = 0$$

An L-contact manifold is called an almost LS-Sasakian manifold, if

$$(2.12) \quad (a) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) + (B_Y \nabla F)(Z, X) + (B_Z \nabla F)(X, Y) - 4\{A(X)\nabla F(Y, Z) + A(Y)\nabla F(Z, X) + A(Z)\nabla F(X, Y)\} = 0$$

This gives

$$(b) \quad (B_{\bar{X}} \nabla F)(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) + (B_{\bar{Y}} \nabla F)(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}) + (B_{\bar{Z}} \nabla F)(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) = 0$$

An L-Contact manifold is called a generalized L-Co-symplectic manifold, if

$$(2.13) \quad (a) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(Y, Z) + A(Y)(B_X A)(\bar{Z}) - A(Z)(B_X A)(\bar{Y}) = 0$$

This gives

$$(b) \quad (B_X \nabla F)(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) = 0$$

An L-Contact manifold is called a generalised nearly L-Cosymplectic manifold, if

$$(2.14) \text{ (a)} \quad (B_X \lrcorner F)(Y, Z) + A(Y)(B_X A)(\bar{Z}) - A(Z)(B_X A)(\bar{Y}) \\ = (B_Y \lrcorner F)(Z, X) + A(Z)(B_Y A)(\bar{X}) - A(X)(B_Y A)(\bar{Z}) \\ = (B_Z \lrcorner F)(X, Y) + A(X)(B_Z A)(\bar{Y}) - A(Y)(B_Z A)(\bar{X})$$

This gives

$$(b) \quad (B_{\bar{X}} \lrcorner F)(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) = (B_{\bar{Y}} \lrcorner F)(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}) = (B_{\bar{Z}} \lrcorner F)(\bar{X}, \bar{Y})$$

An L-Contact manifold is called a generalized almost L-Co-symplectic manifold, if

$$(2.15) \text{ (a)} \quad (B_X \lrcorner F)(Y, Z) + (B_Y \lrcorner F)(Z, X) + (B_Z \lrcorner F)(X, Y) - A(X)\{(B_Y A)(\bar{Z}) - (B_Z A)(\bar{Y})\} \\ - A(Y)\{(B_Z A)(\bar{X}) - (B_X A)(\bar{Z})\} - A(Z)\{(B_X A)(\bar{Y}) - (B_Y A)(\bar{X})\} = 0$$

Which implies

$$(b) \quad (B_{\bar{X}} \lrcorner F)(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) + (B_{\bar{Y}} \lrcorner F)(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}) + (B_{\bar{Z}} \lrcorner F)(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) = 0$$

PROPERTIES

From (2.5) (a), we see that in an LS – Sasakian manifold, $B_T F = 0$. We will now consider nearly LS-Sasakian manifold

Putting T for X in (2.7), we get

$$(3.1) \quad (B_T \lrcorner F)(Y, Z) = -(B_Y A)(\bar{Z}) + 2 \lrcorner F(Y, Z) = (B_Z A)(\bar{Y}) + 2 \lrcorner F(Y, Z)$$

Hence

$$(3.2) \text{ (a)} \quad (B_Y A)(\bar{Z}) + (B_Z A)(\bar{Y}) = 0 \Leftrightarrow (b) \quad B_T T = 0$$

Barring Y and Z in equation (3.1) and then using (2.4) and (3.2), we get

$$(3.3) \quad (B_T \lrcorner F)(Y, Z) = -(B_{\bar{Y}} A)(Z) - 2 \lrcorner F(Y, Z) = (B_{\bar{Z}} A)(Y) - 2 \lrcorner F(Y, Z)$$

From (3.1) and (3.3), we obtain

$$(3.4) \text{ (a)} \quad (B_{\bar{Y}} A)(Z) + (B_Z A)(\bar{Y}) = -4 \lrcorner F(Y, Z) \quad (b) \quad (B_Y A)(Z) + (B_Z A)(Y) = -4g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z})$$

Hence, on a nearly LS-Sasakian manifold, (3.1), (3.2), (3.3) and (3.4) hold.

Almost LS-Sasakian manifold will now be considered. Putting T for X in (2.12) (a), we get

$$(3.5) \text{ (a)} \quad (B_T \lrcorner F)(Y, Z) = (B_Y A)(\bar{Z}) - (B_Z A)(\bar{Y}) - 4 \lrcorner F(Y, Z) \Leftrightarrow (b) \quad B_T T = 0$$

Barring Y and Z in equation (3.5) (a) and using (2.4), we get

$$(3.6) \quad (B_T \lrcorner F)(Y, Z) = (B_{\bar{Y}} A)(Z) - (B_{\bar{Z}} A)(Y) + 4 \lrcorner F(Y, Z)$$

From (3.5) (a) and (3.6), we obtain

$$(3.7) \text{ (a)} \quad (B_{\bar{Y}} A)(Z) - (B_Y A)(\bar{Z}) - (B_{\bar{Z}} A)(Y) + (B_Z A)(\bar{Y}) + 8 \lrcorner F(Y, Z) = 0 \Leftrightarrow$$

$$(b) \quad (B_{\bar{Y}} A)(\bar{Z}) + (B_{\bar{Z}} A)(\bar{Y}) + (B_Y A)(Z) + (B_Z A)(Y) + 8g(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) = 0$$

from (2.7) and (2.14) (a), we see that

A nearly LS-Sasakian manifold is a generalized nearly L-Co-symplectic manifold, if

$$(3.8) \text{ (a)} \quad (B_X A)(\bar{Y}) = 2 \lrcorner F(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) \Leftrightarrow (b) \quad (B_X A)(Y) = -2g(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) \Leftrightarrow (c) \quad B_X T = 2\bar{X}$$

Also, Making the use of (2.12) (a) and (2.15) (a), we see that

A generalized almost L-Co-symplectic manifold is an almost LS-Sasakian manifold, if

$$(3.9) \quad (B_X A)(\bar{Y}) - (B_Y A)(\bar{X}) = 4 \lrcorner F(X, Y)$$

NIJENHUIS TENSOR

In an L-Contact manifold with the semi-symmetric metric connection B , Nijenhuis tensor is given by

$$(4.1) \quad \lrcorner N(X, Y, Z) = (B_{\bar{X}} \lrcorner F)(Y, Z) + (B_{\bar{Y}} \lrcorner F)(Z, X) + (B_X \lrcorner F)(Y, \bar{Z}) + (B_Y \lrcorner F)(\bar{Z}, X)$$

Where

$$\lrcorner N(X, Y, Z) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} g(N(X, Y), Z)$$

Barring X, Y, Z in (4.1) and using equations (2.7), we see that a nearly LS-Sasakian manifold is completely integrable, if

$$(4.2) \quad (B_{\bar{X}} \lrcorner F)(\bar{Y}, \bar{Z}) + (B_{\bar{Y}} \lrcorner F)(\bar{Z}, \bar{X}) = 0.$$

Barring X, Y, Z in (4.1) and using equations (2.12) (b), we can prove that an almost LS-Sasakian manifold is completely integrable, if

$$(4.3) \quad (B_{\bar{Z}}F)(\bar{X}, \bar{Y}) = 0.$$

INDUCED CONNECTION IN AN LS-SASAKIAN MANIFOLD

Let M_{2m-1} be submanifold of M_{2m+1} and let $c : M_{2m-1} \rightarrow M_{2m+1}$ be the inclusion map such that

$$d \in M_{2m-1} \rightarrow cd \in M_{2m+1},$$

Where c induces a linear transformation (Jacobian map) $J : T'_{2m-1} \rightarrow T'_{2m+1}$.

T'_{2m-1} is a tangent space to M_{2m-1} at point d and T'_{2m+1} is a tangent space to M_{2m+1} at point cd such that

$$\hat{X} \text{ in } M_{2m-1} \text{ at } d \rightarrow J\hat{X} \text{ in } M_{2m+1} \text{ at } cd$$

Let \tilde{g} be the induced Lorentzian metric in M_{2m-1} . Then we have

$$(5.1) \quad \tilde{g}(\hat{X}, \hat{Y}) = (g(J\hat{X}, J\hat{Y}))b$$

We now suppose that a semi-symmetric metric connection B in an LS-Sasakian manifold is given by

$$(5.2) \quad B_X Y = D_X Y + A(Y)X - g(X, Y)T,$$

Where X and Y are arbitrary vector fields of M_{2m+1} . If

$$(5.3) \quad T_1 = Jt_1 - \rho_1 M - \sigma_1 N$$

Where t_1 is C^∞ vector fields in M_{2m-1} and M and N are unit normal vectors to M_{2m-1} .

Denoting by \hat{D} the connection induced on the submanifold from D , Let

$$(5.4) \quad D_{JX} J\hat{Y} = J(\hat{D}_X \hat{Y}) - h(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})M - k(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})N$$

Where h and k are symmetric bilinear functions in M_{2m-1} . Similarly we have

$$(5.5) \quad B_{JX} J\hat{Y} = J(\hat{B}_X \hat{Y}) - p(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})M - q(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})N,$$

Where \hat{B} is the connection induced on the submanifold from B and p, q are symmetric bilinear functions in M_{2m-1} . In consequence of (5.2), we have

$$(5.6) \quad B_{JX} J\hat{Y} = D_{JX} J\hat{Y} + A(J\hat{Y})J\hat{X} - g(J\hat{X}, J\hat{Y})T_1$$

Using (5.4), (5.5) and (5.6), we get

$$(5.7) \quad J(\hat{B}_X \hat{Y}) - p(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})M - q(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})N = J(\hat{D}_X \hat{Y}) - h(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})M - k(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})N + A_1(J\hat{Y})J\hat{X} - g(J\hat{X}, J\hat{Y})T_1$$

Using (5.3), we obtain

$$(5.8) \quad J(\hat{B}_X \hat{Y}) - p(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})M - q(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})N = J(\hat{D}_X \hat{Y}) - h(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})M - k(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})N + a_1(\hat{Y})J\hat{X} - \tilde{g}(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})(Jt_1 - \rho_1 M - \sigma_1 N)$$

$$\text{Where } \tilde{g}(\hat{Y}, t_1) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} a_1(\hat{Y})$$

This implies

$$(5.9) \quad \hat{B}_X \hat{Y} = \hat{D}_X \hat{Y} + a_1(\hat{Y})\hat{X} - \tilde{g}(\hat{X}, \hat{Y})t_1$$

Iff

$$(5.10) \quad \tilde{g}(\hat{X}, \hat{Y}) = \frac{1}{\rho_1} \{ h(\hat{X}, \hat{Y}) - p(\hat{X}, \hat{Y}) \} = \frac{1}{\sigma_1} \{ k(\hat{X}, \hat{Y}) - q(\hat{X}, \hat{Y}) \}$$

Therefore,

Theorem 5.1 The connection induced on a submanifold of an LS-Sasakian manifold with a semi-symmetric metric connection with respect to unit normal vectors M and N is also semi-symmetric metric connection iff (5.10) holds.

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